

APPENDIX A
SYSTEM INSTRUCTION FOR SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

You are an expert at analyzing the sentiment of text. Given a piece of text, rate the sentiment of the text on a scale ranging from extremely negative, negative, neutral, positive, to extremely positive. We want to analyze text based on the given label definitions.

Labels definitions:

- extremely negative: Texts that use extremely negative language or emojis to express intense negative emotions such as hate, disapproval, dissatisfaction, frustration. The overall tone is strongly critical and can be very sarcastic.
- negative: Texts that use moderately negative language to express dissatisfaction, disapproval or discomfort without using extreme language. The overall tone is critical to some extent but tends to be more restrained and less emotionally charged compared to stronger negative sentiments.
- neutral: Texts that lack positive or negative emotions and are typically objective, factual, or balanced, without conveying a clear bias or emotional tone. Text is often straightforward statement of preference or curiosity without expressing strong approval, disapproval, enthusiasm, or dissatisfaction. Additionally, neutrality doesn't necessarily imply a complete absence of emotion but rather a lack of strong, identifiable positive or negative emotional inclinations.
- positive: Texts that use moderately positive language to express satisfaction, approval or admiration but are not overly enthusiastic or intense. Usually adjectives similar to pleasant, satisfactory, encouraging, optimistic, amiable, express mildly positive sentiment.
- extremely positive: Texts that use strongly positive language to express emotions such as extreme enthusiasm, satisfaction, or admiration or use happy emojis. Identify the positive adjectives used and their degree to predict the sentiment. Usually positive adjectives of superlative/comparative degree express super positive sentiment.

Here is the text to analyze:

[[text]]

Think about a rationale step-by-step for making a sentiment scale choice before doing so. Include an explanation of your reasoning. Restrict your response to two lines.

APPENDIX B
SYSTEM INSTRUCTION FOR HUMAN MESSAGE SEPARATION

You are an expert software engineer specializing in parsing and categorizing technical text. Your task is to analyze the provided input text and separate any human-written messages from computer-generated error messages (e.g., compiler errors, stack traces, runtime exceptions).

Labels definitions:

- error_message_only: The text consists solely of an error message.
- human_message_only: The text consists solely of a human-written message.
- mixed_message: The text contains both a human-written message and an error message.

Separation guide:

- If the classification is mixed_message, identify and extract the human-written message.
- If the classification is error_message_only, indicate an empty string for the human message.
- If the classification is human_message_only, extract the human message.

Think about a rationale step-by-step. Include an explanation of your reasoning. Restrict your response to two lines.

Here is the text to analyze:

[[text]]

APPENDIX C
MANUAL ANNOTATION PROTOCOL FOR USER SATISFACTION

The primary objective of manual annotation is to capture the *user's perceived satisfaction*, not the objective correctness of the AI's output, which is extremely challenging to evaluate without having a full understanding of user intent and the task. A label will be assigned to a set of sampled user turns (n^{th} turn in conversation) which indicated satisfaction with the previous AI response ($(n - 1)^{\text{th}}$ turn in conversation).

A. Annotation Process

For each sampled user turn (n^{th} turn), the annotation can follow these steps:

- 1) **Examine the Target Turn:** First, analyze the content of the user's prompt at the n^{th} turn. If the user's satisfaction or dissatisfaction is explicitly stated or strongly implied, assign a label.
- 2) **Examine Surrounding Context:** If the target turn is ambiguous, expand the context to include: (1) the user's previous prompt ($(n - 2)^{\text{th}}$ turn), (2) the AI's response that the user is reacting to ($(n - 1)^{\text{th}}$ turn), (3) the AI's next response ($(n + 1)^{\text{th}}$ turn), as it sometimes contains clues (e.g., an apology).
- 3) **Assign a Label:** Based on the evidence, assign one of the three labels defined below. To maintain efficiency, if a definitive label could not be assigned within approximately 3 minutes of analysis, the turn was labeled 'Cannot Judge'.
- 4) **Handle Non-English Text:** Any prompts written in languages other than English were translated before labeling.

B. Label Definitions and Heuristics

Satisfied A "Satisfied" label can be assigned if the user's prompt indicated that the previous AI response met their needs or made successful progress on their task. Turns with following characteristics can be assigned "Satisfied":

- Explicit appreciation (e.g., "Great!", "Awesome", "thanks!").
- Smooth continuation to a subsequent step (e.g., "Perfect, now can you add comments to that function?").
- Affirmation followed by a new, related request.

Unsatisfied An "Unsatisfied" label was assigned if the user's prompt indicated that the previous AI response was incorrect, unhelpful, or failed to meet their expectations. Turns with following characteristics can be assigned "Unsatisfied":

- Explicit frustration or negative feedback (e.g., "No, that's wrong." "This is useless.").
- Corrective statements pointing out an error in the AI's previous response (e.g., "No! You forgot to handle the null case.").
- A follow-up question phrased as a complaint or pointing out a flaw (e.g., "Why did you use a deprecated library?").
- The AI's subsequent response is an apology (e.g., if the AI says "I apologize for the confusion," it is highly likely the preceding user turn expressed dissatisfaction).
- The user encounters a new error that was directly caused by the AI's last suggestion.

Cannot Judge This label was used when there was insufficient evidence in the conversation to confidently infer the user's satisfaction level. Turns with following characteristics can be assigned "Cannot Judge":

- The user's prompt is a simple statement of a new task or error with no emotional or qualitative language (e.g., a user pastes in a new error message without comment).
- The user's prompt is an unrelated question, indicating a complete context shift from the previous turn.
- The intent is simply too ambiguous to label reliably within the allotted time.

APPENDIX D
ADDITIONAL FIGURES

Fig. 1: Average sentiment score per user.

Fig. 2: Distribution of the number of turns included in each conversation, grouped by the conversation sentiment.